

THE 9TH PRINCIPLE OF GENERAL DENTAL COUNCIL AND ITS RELATION TO PEDIATRIC DENTISTRY

Sonia Bhansali¹

¹Private practitioner, Surat, India

Correspondence: soniabhansali@gmail.com

LETTER TO THE EDITOR

ABSTRACT: *The ninth principle of the dental council is about the ethics of a dentist as a professional. This audio transcript gives an overview of how a dentist's conduct should be on both work and personal front.*

Keywords: *code of ethics, pediatric dentistry, podcasts, public health practices*

How to cite: Bhansali S. The 9th principle of general dental council and its relation to pediatric dentistry. The Quadrant. 2024;2(3):2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13704412>

Sir,

The 9th principle of the General Dental Council is to make sure your personal behavior maintains patient's confidence in you and the dental profession.¹ In short, the dentist conduct both at work and in personal life, justify his patients trust in you and the public's trust in dental profession. It can basically be done by behavior guidance, by asking questions and active or reflective listening which can help establishing trust and rapport. The dentist should not publish anything on any public media which could affect patients and the public's confidence in you or the dental profession unless this is done as a part of raising a council. And here you are not only dealing with the patients but the parents as well. So, at last I want to conclude this broadcast as to be confident in you, your voice and your work which will indirectly have a positive reflection on the patients as well as the parents.

REFERENCES

1. Principle Nine [Internet]. Gdc-uk.org. General Dental Council; 2019. Available from: <https://standards.gdc-uk.org/pages/principle9/principle9.aspx>

Bhansali S. The 9th principle of general dental council and its relation to pediatric dentistry. The Quadrant. 2024;2(3):2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13704412>

